

A Comparative Study to Evaluate the Efficacy and Safety of Vortioxetine and Escitalopram in Patients with Depression**Ronakkumar Chandubhai Patel¹, Anil Kumar², Mahima Singh³, Tapas Kumar Aich⁴, Ajeet Pratap Singh⁵**¹Junior Resident (Final Year), Department of Pharmacology, BRD Medical College, Gorakhpur, UP, India²Associate Professor & Nodal Head, Department of Pharmacology, BRD Medical College, Gorakhpur, UP, India³Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, BRD Medical College, Gorakhpur, UP, India⁴Professor & Head, Department of Psychiatry, BRD Medical College, Gorakhpur, UP, India⁵Associate Professor, Department of Medicine, BRD Medical College, Gorakhpur, UP, India

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Depression is a serious mental disease, with very serious consequences for people and for the health systems. The goals of this research are to evaluate the effectiveness, demographic distribution, and associated clinical variables with escitalopram and vortioxetine treatment of depression.**Methods:** Out of the 74 subjects with an ICD 10 diagnosis of depression, 37 received escitalopram and 37 were given vortioxetine. Examined were multiple demographic, clinical and treatment response variables: gender, comorbidities and their clinical enhancement measured by the Clinical Global Impression severity (CGI-S) over the course of a period of six weeks. Significance ($p < 0.05$) of the results were ascertained by using statistical analyses.**Results:** No significant difference between groups constituted the gender distribution with about equal representation. Treatment allocation was not affected substantially by the size or structure of the family. The distribution of severity of diagnosis and frequency of prior depressive episodes was equally distributed among the groups. At six weeks therapy, CGI-S scores indicated clinical enhancement for both groups, with no differences between vortioxetine and escitalopram being significant at any time point. Incidence and hospitalization of hypertension were similar between groups.**Conclusion:** There were no significant differences in effectiveness or tolerability for either escitalopram or vortioxetine in relieving depression symptoms. Both medications show promising potential effectiveness as alternatives to treat depression and may allow customizing therapy according to patient wish, current clinical circumstances.**Keywords:** Depression, Escitalopram, Vortioxetine, Clinical Global Impression-Severity (CGI-S), Treatment efficacy.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Depressive illness is a common, chronic and recurrent mental health problem that is a leading cause of disability globally, afflicting some 350 million people worldwide. Numerous primary symptoms constitute the syndrome, including prolonged sorrow, considerable lack of interest in activities, and greatly reduced activity levels [1,2]. However, these symptoms can have a major impact on an individual's social functioning and represent a large illness burden [3]. Additionally, individuals suffering from depressive illnesses are subject to great and profound cognitive impairment [4, 5]. One of the nine defining criteria of the depressive episodes according to American Diagnostic and

Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-4 and DSM-5) is the cognitive symptom [6]. It is known that cognitive impairment persisting after amelioration of depressed symptoms is a major impediment to full restoration of social functioning in the individuals with depressive disorders [7,8]. Pharmacotherapy still remains the primary treatment for depressive disorders in the clinic. Escape with the safest and most effective as a selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI) since the introduction of Escitalopram in 2002. In a large double blind, placebo-controlled clinical research using 380 patients with depressive disorders escitalopram at 10 mg daily was found to be

efficacious compared to placebo after only two weeks [9]. Another study into long term pharmacological therapy looked at 274 patients over 36 weeks in a randomised, double blinded experiment which further provides additional evidence of its effectiveness. The result of this study showed continuous improvement in patients' overall MADRS score until the end of the 36 week duration of therapy, [10] which supported the benefit of continued treatment. Vortioxetine, a new antidepressant, won a market authorization in the USA in May 2013 and in China in November 2017. Essentially, this medicine represents a novel multi modal approach to treating depression which engages six pharmacological targets and two distinct mechanisms of action [11]. Studies in global research have demonstrated its efficacy and safety for depression treatment, and its favorable effects on patients' cognitive and social function [12,13]. A large research of 156 senior individuals over 65 years old showed vortioxetine to be very effective as opposed to placebo over an eight week treatment period. This study specifically emphasized the medication's capacity to improve cognitive function, assessed using two neuropsychological assessments: The Digit Symbol Substitution Test (DSST) and the Rey Auditory Verbal Learning Test (RAVLT) [14]. Research has been sparse following the introduction to the Chinese market of vortioxetine in 2017 [15]. Research to date has principally been to assess the mood-related symptoms without thoroughly investigating the cognitive and social function improvements. In addition, no randomized controlled trials exist comparing vortioxetine to escitalopram. The purpose of this research is to finally determine the safety and effectiveness of both drugs on people with depressive disorders using several treatment approaches. The aim of this study is to deepen the evidence based comprehension of these two antidepressants, to provide improved recommendations for therapeutic use [15].

Material and Methods

This study is registered in the Clinical Trials Registry - India (CTRI) and CTRI No. is CTRI/2023/12/060661. The selection approach was specifically aimed at study eligible patients with Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) who met all treatment eligibility criteria indicated by the study protocol. For their study, the research team used statistical data from previous studies that pointed to

an average depression prevalence rate of 4.5 in India, to estimate a sample size that was appropriate for the study. Statistical analyses were based upon a 95% confidence interval with a 0.05 margin of error, and maintained scientific rigor. The team utilized a conventional statistical formula for sample size determination: The sample size, n , required equals to $n = Z^2P(1-P)/d^2$, where n is the sample size, $Z = 1.96$ (for 95 % confidence level), $P = 0.045$ (or 4.5 % prevalence) and $d = 0.05$ (or 5 % precision). This algorithm use has indicated that a minimum 66 participants are needed to obtain statistically meaningful research findings. The research team acknowledged participant attrition and potential data collecting inaccuracies while the study was ongoing. To account for these concerns, they increased the number of calculated participants by 10% to bring a final total of 74 persons. This modification made the statistical validity of this study possible even when the participants withdrew or samples were unusable. Explicit inclusion criteria were defined for the participant for the research. Before to registration, all participants were mandated to give written informed consent.

Regardless of gender, the accepted participants were 18 to 60 years old. They included eligible participants with a current ICD-10 depression diagnosis, with or without somatic symptoms, recurrent depression. If the present depressed episode is depressed, then it has to be at least 4 weeks to at least a 1 year in length. Furthermore, participants were required to achieve designated scoring thresholds on standardized evaluations: in the first appointment, when they score 7-34 on the Montgomery Asberg Depression Rating Scale (MADRS) and a Clinical Global Impression Severity (CGI-S) score of 2-6. Exclusion criteria as rigorous concerning the mental health problems were established. Subjects with a history or current diagnosis of schizophrenia, schizophreniform disease, delusional disorder, schizoaffective disorder, or any unspecified psychotic illness were not included as investigational subjects. The list also included bipolar disease, alcohol or drug use disorders, or eating disorders or obsessive compulsive disorder or biological mental illness such as dementia. In addition, subjects with history of electric convulsive treatment, seizure disorder or pregnant or lactating women were ineligible to participate in the study.

Results

Table 1: Gender profile

Gender	Escitalopram	Vortioxetine	Total	P-value
Male	21	18	39	0.485
Female	16	19	35	
Total	37	37	74	

Table 1: The gender profile indicated no significant difference ($p=0.485$) between male and female distributions in the escitalopram and vortioxetine groups. This guarantees the lack of bias in treatment outcome by gender results.

Table 2: Montgomery-Åsberg Depression Rating Scale (MADRS)

Week	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
0 Week	Vortioxetine	37	26.70	4.274	0.014
	Escitalopram	37	27.62	2.861	
2 Week	Vortioxetine	37	23.24	4.722	0.002
	Escitalopram	37	24.57	2.555	
4 Week	Vortioxetine	37	18.35	5.350	0.008
	Escitalopram	37	19.59	3.395	
6 Week	Vortioxetine	37	12.19	3.872	0.566
	Escitalopram	37	12.86	3.473	

Table 2: The table presents data from the Montgomery-Åsberg Depression Rating Scale at 0 weeks, 2 weeks, 4 weeks, and 6 weeks for patients receiving Vortioxetine and Escitalopram. The P values indicate the statistical significance of differences in mean scores between the two groups at each time point, except at 6 week, p value is 0.566.

Table 3: Diagnosis report

Diagnosis (as per ICD-10)	Escitalopram	Vortioxetine	Group Total	P-value
Mild depression	6	8	14	0.938
Moderate depression	18	16	34	
Severe depression without psychosis	8	7	15	
Recurrent depression with current mild depression	4	4	8	
Recurrent depression with current moderate depression	1	2	3	
Total	37	37	74	

Table 3: The results are consistent with a comparably distributed degree of depression among escitalopram and vortioxetine groups ($p=0.938$). What this means is both therapies are evenly represented across different levels of depression severity.

Table 4: Depression treatment

Previous Depressive Episodes	Escitalopram	Vortioxetine	Group Total	P-value
Yes	5	6	11	0.744
No	32	31	63	
Total	37	37	74	

Table 4: No large difference is observed between the escitalopram and vortioxetine cohorts in terms of prior depressive episodes ($p=0.744$). The uniformity of the history of depression over the two treatment groups demonstrates this.

Table 5: Hypertension disorders

Hypertension	Escitalopram	Vortioxetine	Group Total	P-value
Yes	11	11	22	1.00
No	26	26	52	
Total	37	37	74	

Table 5: The hypertension analysis shows there is no significant between group difference in number of individuals with hypertension ($p=1.00$). And this means that hypertension is equally present in both treatment groups and it doesn't affect the allocation of treatment.

Table 6: Number of Hospitalizations

Hospitalizations	Escitalopram	Vortioxetine	Group Total	P-value
Yes	11	7	18	0.278
No	26	30	56	
Total	37	37	74	

Table 6: We found no significant difference in the number of hospitalization between the escitalopram and vortioxetine groups ($p=0.278$). This means that in terms of rates of hospitalization, we don't see a difference between the two therapy groups.

Table 7: Clinical Global Impression- Scale (CGI-S) scale

Time Point	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P-value
0 Week	Vortioxetine	37	5.14	0.631	0.432
	Escitalopram	37	5.16	0.688	
2 Week	Vortioxetine	37	5.03	0.600	0.087
	Escitalopram	37	4.76	0.683	
4 Week	Vortioxetine	37	4.19	0.776	0.607
	Escitalopram	37	3.89	0.737	
6 Week	Vortioxetine	37	2.95	0.524	0.237
	Escitalopram	37	2.86	0.585	

Table 7: Both vortioxetine and escitalopram cohorts show progressive improvement on the CGI-S ratings over 6 weeks with no statistically significant between group differences at any time point ($p > 0.05$). In both of these medications, this implies similar efficacy over time in treating depression. The rates of adverse events like anorexia, nausea, vomiting were similarly well tolerated in both of the two therapies.

Discussion

MADRS scores were significantly reduced in patients receiving the serotonin receptor modulator vortioxetine in comparison with the partial agonist 5-HT1A receptor agonist vilazodone or the SSRI escitalopram. The side effects were generally minor and not serious, and patients' safety profile was better in the vortioxetine group. The results were in agreement with that of the interim analysis of this study and two earlier meta-analyses [16, 17, 18, 21]. In the second group, the dosages of vilazodone were 20–40 mg per day; in the first group, vortioxetine was within the dose range of 5–20 mg per day.

The control group was treated with escitalopram at dosages of 10–20 mg per day. Vilazodone is a partial 5HT1A receptor agonist and has some benefits over escitalopram, in that it is a serotonergic reuptake inhibitor (SSRI). Vortioxetine as an antagonist of serotonin transport and receptor activity interacts with serotonin receptors. Participants were divided into two groups that administered vortioxetine, and the group administered vortioxetine had statistically significant results.

Hence, in some of these groups, marked decreases in HDRS and MADRS scores were also observed accompanying the procedures. Consequently, vortioxetine monotherapy can be an appropriate treatment approach for major depressive disorder (MDD). During the trial, no volunteers were paid for the medicines irrespective of which group they had been slotted into. However, the prediction is that it must have a minimal dropout rate due to the significant score improvements and the decrease in depressive symptoms. It could rather have helped in ensuring the effectiveness of the drugs as antidepressants. A statistically highly significant

comparison of HDRS and MADRS scores and spectrum of adverse events in the vortioxetine group compared to other trial groups. The outcome showed that vortioxetine would be a significant adjunct in the treatment of major depressive disorder in the coming future [16, 21].

A recent network meta-analysis [20] suggests that the most efficient approach to improving the efficacy of antidepressants depends on decreasing the dropout rate, measuring different aspects of depression symptoms, and reducing side effects. This study covers all these areas, and the findings are substantial. This is consistent with the interim analysis of the study [17,18, 19]. Its strengths include the use of permuted block randomization and the assessment of Major Depressive Disorder using two validated scales: the HDRS and the MADRS. Periodical analyses and evaluations of both cohorts: ITT and PP, served as supplementary research.

However, there are room for improvement. Because of the open label design of the study, the dropout rate and reporting of adverse events may increase and the study's short duration may not encompass long term effects or delayed onset negative effects. Additionally, these findings only apply when these therapies are economically as well as commercially viable and available in that locality. Antidepressants are not uniformly effective over time in 'real world' situations and depression is inherently complex [20].

Conclusion

The objective of this research is to evaluate vortioxetine and escitalopram efficacy and safety in major depressive disorder (MDD) across assorted demographic and clinical factors. This demonstrated that there were no differences between the therapies with regard to effectiveness or safety, with no significant difference in all the categories on which we investigated. Both groups were evaluated in similarly severe patients, both consistent at the diagnostic severity of depression. Clinical Global Impression Scale (CGI-S) as measure of clinical outcomes presented with the same improvement in the vortioxetine and escitalopram cohorts, but without a statistically significant difference between the two groups. The

fact both drugs equalized depressed symptoms suggests there was no drug which was superior in alleviation of depressed symptoms and none superior regarding treatment results. The rates of hypertension prevalence, hospitalization, and adverse events were similarly well tolerated in both of the two therapies, and there were no significant changes, the research showed. Overall, both vortioxetine and escitalopram were able to manage depression, although with similar areas of safety and treatment outcomes.

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